

Optimisation of a tram wheel profile using a biologically inspired algorithm

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Highlights

- A multibody simulation-based wheel profile optimisation algorithm was proposed.
- Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy was used to develop the algorithm.
- Track irregularities and vehicle structure were taken into consideration.
- The new wheel profile achieved a better wear index and derailment coefficient.

Abstract

The friction pair formed by wheel and rail is subject to adhesive wear, which leads to a waste of time and money. The wear is inevitable but can be slowed down with the proper design of the wheel profile. This paper formalises the problem of automatic wheel profile design as a constrained optimisation and presents an efficient method of solving it using a state-of-the-art biologically-inspired black-box optimisation algorithm. The algorithm is multi-objective, in that it optimises not only the wheel and rail wear but also ride safety. The optimisation was performed for rail conditions in the city of Poznań, Poland. The performed simulations show that profiles obtained that way significantly outperform the ones currently used in Poznań in terms of wear index and derailment coefficient, which makes the new solution worth verifying experimentally and possibly putting into operation.

Keywords: wheel-rail contact, shape optimisation, genetic algorithm, wheel profile, light rail vehicle

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Wheel profile is a very commonly discussed issue in railway related papers and events. Indeed, its geometry has considerable impact on vehicle dynamics. That is, among other factors, on ride safety and wheel-rail interface wear [1–3]. Although the wheel-rail interface consists of two elements, introducing new shapes of wheel profiles is easier, less expensive and less laborious than altering rail profiles. Every rolling stock operator has the means to reprofile wheels either with their own lathe or through outsourcing to another company, while changing the rail profile requires the grinding of rails at the very least (for small or gradual changes) [4] or replacing rails on long sections of track, which is a huge undertaking. More importantly, even the most sophisticated and dedicated wheel profile is subject to variable environmental and technical conditions of operation, which can alter its characteristics [5]. Furthermore, it is unfeasible to design a single wheel profile that is best, regardless of its purposes [6]. Objectives will usually conflict and compromises need to be made. To conclude, wheel profile optimisation is the art of reaching compromises between selected objective function parameters.

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1.2. Related work

Much research has been done on the subject of railway wheel-rail interface. However, works on tram wheel-rail interface are far less numerous and are less advanced. Wheel profile optimisation is just one of a variety of wheel-rail interface issues. Generally, wheel profile optimisation research may be divided into the following groups, according to the applied methodology:

- genetic algorithm (GA) [7–9],
- target rolling radius difference (RRD) [2,10–13],
- target contact angle function or target conicity, closely related to RRD [14,15],
- normal gap between wheel and rail [16],

among which only [9,13] concerned light rail vehicle applications. Some of the above papers [8,11,13,17] used multibody simulation software to assess the dynamic performance of the proposed solutions. Optimisation using target functions seems to be the least time consuming from the above list. The dynamic performance of the resultant wheel profile is carried out after optimisation only to check the correctness of the design process that has taken place. The normal gap method assumes that a small clearance between wheel and rail in the contact patch neighbourhood contributes to more conformal contact shape and to a reduction in contact stress level (including rolling contact fatigue) [16]. A bio-inspired heuristic search for the best solution through successive generations of candidate solutions is the essence of GA [18]. The assessment of candidate solutions must be carried out for every one of them, which makes this method more time consuming. On the other hand, the algorithm is not constrained by any target function (it may be determined intuitively) but struggles to meet the requirements of the objective function. Many more potential wheel profiles are examined with this method. We decided to use the genetic approach, which is described in the section below.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Preliminary research on tram wheel damage

The aim of the optimisation process was to automatically design a new wheel profile for a low-floor tram from the city of Poznań, Poland. In order to understand the main mechanisms of wheel wear, a preliminary research involving measurements of wheel profile wear from two low-floor trams used in Poznań was undertaken. The results of this research are summarised in Fig. 1. The lines indicate individual measurements, which were carried out from the moment of leaving the underfloor wheel lathe by the vehicle (marked as initial) until the next reprofiling. The following notation for wheels was applied – $WSxy$, where x is the axle number counting from the front of the vehicle, and y indicates the side of the vehicle, R for right and L for left.

Fig. 1 Measured wheel profiles from the first bogies: a) low-floor tram #1 (classic wheelsets, non-pivoting bogie), b) low-floor tram #2 (independent wheels, non-pivoting bogie)

The relationships between wheel flange geometry (width and height) and vehicle mileage were presented in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. The following conclusions were formulated:

- Attacking wheelsets on low-floor trams wear more than those at the rear. A similar effect was observed in bogies, where the wheels of the first bogie wear more than the others'.
- Rear wheelsets showed signs of plastic deformation in the form of overhangs. The phenomenon was far less intense on attacking wheels, which is possibly due to the higher angle of attack and wearing of the deformed material. This means that the phenomenon is possibly also present on the attacking wheelsets, but its effects are being quickly eliminated by wear.
- Plastic deformation of the rear wheelset's flange tips contributed to an increase in flange width at the beginning of their service.
- The largest loss of wheel material is observed in the area of the flange, caused by wear and plastic deformation.
- Hollow wear is present on all wheels.

Fig. 2 Flange width versus mileage, low-floor tram #1 (classic wheelsets, non-pivoting bogie)

Fig. 3 Flange height versus mileage, low-floor tram #1 (classic wheelsets, non-pivoting bogie)

Two samples of wheel rim materials were taken from low-floor tram #1 (WS1R and WS2R). The analysis was carried out within the same research project as this manuscript. Further details may be found in [19–21]. The chemical composition of the samples (steel P70) was (% of mass): 0.629-0.664 C, 0.894-0.932 Mn, 0.262-0.278 Si, 0.0009-0.016 P and 0.010-0.011 S. Values below 0.011 are beyond the apparatus accreditation. The core material is characterised by its perlitic-ferritic microstructure with a perlite predominance. The average hardness is about 300 HV0.1. The macroscopic analysis of the surface of the tested rims allows for the recognition of abrasion due to full slip (e.g., tight curves) or partial slip (high longitudinal forces, traction, braking etc.). As a result, the surface of the wheel rim was being temporarily heated and weakened by cracks initiating and developing into surface defects, called shells, according to the shelling mechanism, which is a common form of damage in the tested samples (Fig. 4). The influence of the third bodies (wear products, oxides, sand etc.) pressed into the wheel rim material was also noticed. Most of the effects were observed on rolling surfaces. It should be noted that shelling was at an early stage of development. The resultant chipping was small and not present around the whole circumference of the rim. Moreover, on small areas of the surface, white layer was observed. Due to the thermal conditions of its formation, it should be assumed that there was a local heating of sliding rolling surfaces which was greater than what there was for shelling. However, it was a local process, not having a key meaning in the general course of damage [19].

Fig. 4 SEM pictures of the wheel rim material: a) shelling (rolling surface), b) micro-cracks that initiate shelling (rolling surface), c) delamination near the flange tip, d) plastic deformation on the rolling surface [19]

The observations proved the presence of plastic deformations (Fig. 4c, Fig. 4d and Fig. 5) on the rolling surface and near the flange tip. In these places, the presence of manganese sulphide was also observed, which may promote the formation of cracks. White etching layer was also noticed which usually forms on rails where austenitisation temperature occurs due to creepage or where plastic deformation is developing [22].

The strong plastic deformation induced strain-hardening of the wheel rim surface (Fig. 6). The HV0.1 hardness of the flange tip increased almost twofold compared to the core hardness. The hardness of the rolling surface also increased, but to a much lesser extent. This is probably due to the larger contact area and lower contact stress. Along with hardening, the wheel surface is becoming more brittle. It should be noted that strain-hardening of the material had a lesser effect on the attacking wheelset. The strain-hardness influenced area reaches up to 0.1 mm in depth, while the material of the attacking wheels is being wearing more intensively.

Fig. 5 Overhang at the outer end of wheel profile [19]

Fig. 6 Material hardness versus distance from the surface (due to strain hardening), RS – rolling surface, FT – flange tip [19]

To conclude, the most important outcomes for the optimisation process discovered during preliminary research are as follows. Wear is one of the dominating damage mechanisms of tram wheels, hence a wear-dependent coefficient must be picked and minimised. Relatively high axle loads (typically exceeding 100 kN per axle) induce plastic deformations of wheel rims, most strongly in the wheel flange area. This causes strain-hardening of the wheel surface making it more brittle and prone to cracks. A measure to reduce contact stress must be taken.

2.2. Objective function

To obtain a new wheel profile, we decided to optimise three criteria: $f1$ – wear index I_w (the maximum mean wear index over time and over the four wagon wheels), $f2$ – Y/Q_{ratio} (the maximum over the four wheels and over the whole track), $f3$ – contact area A_c (the

maximum over the four wheels). The wear index was calculated according to the formula (1), where F_x and F_y are creep forces (longitudinal and lateral, respectively), s_x and s_y are linear creepages (longitudinal and lateral, respectively), θ stands for spin moment and ω for spin creepage. Different wheel profiles have different flange inclinations thus the Y/Q_{lim} limit is variable. To make various wheel profiles comparable, the Y/Q_{ratio} is proposed (2), which describes the proximity to derailment in a range from 0 to 1.

$$f1 = I_w = |F_x s_x| + |F_y s_y| + |\theta \omega| \quad (1)$$

$$f2 = Y/Q_{ratio} = \frac{Y/Q}{Y/Q_{lim}} \quad (2)$$

The wear index and Y/Q_{ratio} were to be minimised while the contact area was to be maximised. Technically, we minimise the negated value of the contact area. All three function values are computed using multibody simulation with Simpack, in our case. Special care had to be taken when calculating Y/Q_{ratio} , since it was prone to sudden peaks, which should be treated as artefacts.

Fig. 7 Y/Q simulation artefact example (WS1R – first wheelset, right wheel)

In order to eliminate the peaks, we applied a low-pass Hampel filter. Its function is similar to the well-known median filter. However, the Hampel filter, in contrast to the median one, does not treat all peaks equally. It applies the filtering window only if the window median is above a certain threshold. We used a threshold of 1.0 and a window size of 13. An example of the time series filtered by the Hampel filter is shown in Fig. 7. The green line is the original time series while the filtered peaks are shown with a dashed line.

2.3. Wheel profile model

Fig. 8 Wheel profile for optimisation

The wheel profile (see Fig. 8) was modelled by the function $profile(y)$ (3) which consists of five parts: a cubic spline curve, two fillets with the radius $r = 3$ mm, an arc of a circle with the radius $R = 240$ mm and a straight line. The wheel profile was 90 mm wide; it begins in point A for $y_A = -32.5$ mm, goes through the origin and ends in point E for $y_E = 57.5$ mm.

$$profile(y) = \begin{cases} spline(y), & -32.5 \leq y < y_{C_1} \\ fillet_1(y), & y_{C_1} \leq y \leq y_{C_2} \\ arc(y), & y_{C_2} \leq y \leq y_{D_1} \\ fillet_2(y), & y_{D_1} \leq y \leq y_{D_2} \\ line(y), & y_{D_2} \leq y \leq 57.5 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The conditions of the tangency at the ends of functions $fillet_1(y)$ and $fillet_2(y)$, i.e. at points C_1, C_2, D_1, D_2 , were satisfied by the functions $spline(y)$, $arc(y)$ and $line(y)$. The minimum value of the function $arc(y)$ was -22 mm. The steepness of the function $line(y)$ was 5:1 and the intersection with point E occurred at coordinates $(57.5, z_E)$, where $z_E = 5$ was initially set. In Fig. 8, which outlines the wheel profile model, the optimisation region was described with a cubic spline from point A to point C_1 . The shaded region was not a subject of analysis, although the algorithm was able to control the flange shape. The feasibility conditions of the spline were as follows:

- the vertical values z decrease between point A to point C_1 ,
- the concavity is in the interval $(-10, y_{C_1})$,
- the flange inclination in point B is in the $(60^\circ, 75^\circ)$ range,
- the minimum radius of the flange root curvature is 13 mm, which is equal to the 49E1 rail gauge corner radius.

These conditions were implemented in the function $feasible(x)$, which checks if all of the above-mentioned conditions are satisfied, which means that solution x is feasible. The number of spline knots was set to $m + n - 1$, where n and m are the number of knots with the nonpositive and nonnegative value of y coordinate, respectively. The number -1 in the sum $m + n - 1$ is for handling point $(0,0)$ which, otherwise, would be counted twice.

2.4. Optimisation algorithm

2.4.1. Optimisation problem statement

From the optimisation perspective, the problem of wheel profile optimisation is stated as follows. Each candidate solution to our problem is a cubic spline, which is encoded as a vector of real numbers $x \in X$, where X is the search space we consider. In our problem, $X = R^{2n+2m-2}$, where m and n , were set to 18 and 11 respectively, thus $X = R^{56}$. Note, however, that the computation resources at our disposal did not allow us to extensively search the space of m and n , thus our choice might be suboptimal.

The goal of the optimisation problem is defined by three objective functions or optimisation criteria f_1 , f_2 , and f_3 which need to be minimised, thus one cannot expect a single solution minimising all (conflicting) objectives. The analytic form of these functions is unavailable and, therefore, the considered problem belongs to a class of multi-objective black-box optimisation problems.

To compare candidate solutions in multi-objective optimisation problems, we used a notion of dominance. The candidate solution $a \in X$ dominates another candidate solution $b \in X$ ($dominates(a, b)$) if, and only if, a is not worse than b in all the criteria and better than b in at least one. If neither a dominates b nor b dominates a , then a and b are non-dominated.

In light of this, the goal of our optimisation problem is to find a set of solutions $S \subseteq X$ so that no solution exists $x \in X$ that dominates any of $s \in S$. Such a set of solutions is also known as

the Pareto front. Notice that the definition of the Pareto front implies that the elements of S are mutually non-dominated.

In theory, the Pareto front can be infinite. Given limited computational resources, we therefore cannot expect to find all the elements of S . From a practical perspective, S should be as versatile as possible, consisting of solutions exhibiting various trade-offs in terms of the optimisation criteria. If the ultimate practical goal is to provide a single solution to the problem, it is the role of a domain expert to select the single “best” solution from the Pareto front. The contents of set S can provide valuable information about the trade-offs that have to be made and thus facilitate the process of selection for the “best” solution.

2.4.2. Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy

To solve the considered optimisation problem, we employed CMA-ES (Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy), a state-of-the-art continuous black-box optimisation algorithm [23]. The optimisation problem is a multi-objective one, hence a multi-objective variant of CMA-ES was used [24].

CMA-ES is an iterative algorithm. In every iteration, it generates a number of candidate solutions from a multivariate Gaussian distribution. The distribution is described by a covariance matrix, which, in turn, is updated based on the fitnesses of the candidate solutions (i.e. the values of the three optimisation criteria). CMA-ES is a local optimisation algorithm. To bring the results closer to the global optimum, we executed it several times from different starting points. Each such run lasted from 2 to 10 days. The computations have been performed on an 8-core i7 CPU.

2.4.3. The fitness function

The fitness function returns a vector of three numbers which correspond to the optimisation criteria. Since the optimisation objectives were of different scales, they have been rescaled so that the results roughly fall into the range of $[-1, 1]$. The lower the fitness values, the better.

2.4.4. Unfeasible candidate solution handling

In each iteration, CMA-ES generates a number of candidate solutions, whose fitness is evaluated. Some of them might be unfeasible. Thus, some means of handling unfeasible candidate solutions had to be implemented. One method would be to set the fitness of an unfeasible candidate solution to an arbitrarily high value. This way, the CMA-ES algorithm is implicitly informed that a given part of the search space should be avoided. This, however, may mean that in each generation, we could have just a few feasible (or even zero) candidate solutions to inform CMA-ES. The preliminary results have shown that this approach is ineffective. That is why, in the case of generating an unfeasible candidate solution, we first try to automatically repair it by adjusting the positions of the unfeasible knots. If the result is still unfeasible, we immediately discard it, and let CMA-ES generate another. We repeat this procedure until we gather a required number of feasible solutions. In some cases, finding a feasible solution takes several seconds.

2.4.5. Optimisation parameters and implementation

The initial step-size of CMA-ES was set to 0.3, and the other CMA-ES parameters at $\mu = 64$, $\lambda = 16$. The optimisation algorithm was implemented in Python with the help of the DEAP (Distributed Evolutionary Algorithms in Python) library [25].

2.4.6. Baseline wheel profiles

In order to be able to objectively evaluate our evolved profiles, we computed the values of the optimisation criteria for a number of baseline “known” tramway wheel profiles from

selected European cities. Those known profiles constitute a baseline for our optimisation. The list of “known” profiles and their basic parameters is provided in Tab. 1.

Tab. 1 List of “known” profiles

id	name	I_w [N]	Y/Q_{ratio} [-]	A_c [m ²]	eq_conicity [-]
1	V15 (UK)	504.43	0.54	2.08e-07	0.06
2	Zurich (Switzerland)	622.88	0.79	7.42e-05	0.02
3	TW (Poland)	340.12	0.80	2.17e-05	0.94
4	VM (Czech Republic)	548.35	1.21	5.24e-05	0.13
5	PST (Poland)	392.38	1.29	3.58e-05	0.44
6	T (Poland)	458.92	1.45	5.86e-05	1.64
7	Bostrab_A (Germany)	565.71	1.85	3.51e-05	0.03
8	FIAT (Italy)	408.95	2.41	3.22e-05	0.84

Only the first three profiles from the above list are non-dominated. Among them, V15 is definitely the best with respect to Y/Q_{ratio} but, at the same time, it is characterised by the worst contact area and a high wear index. TW and Zurich have a worse Y/Q_{ratio} (both around 0.79). TW has the best wear index I_w , while Zurich has the largest contact area A_c . It is important to note that although the “known” profiles constitute an important baseline for our computational experiments, they were adjusted for specific wheelset back to back distances to enable running on tracks under Polish regulations. The above results for “known” profiles do not necessarily reflect their performance in the original conditions.

The optimisation algorithm is depicted in Fig. 9. It consists of 4 main elements. The first – Optimiser is responsible for handling the whole process, data and instructions. Profile Encoder generates a wheel profile shape, which is checked by Feasibility Quick Checker whether it has wheel profile features (feasibility conditions described in 2.3). If the answer is positive, then the wheel profile is exported to the Simpack environment and the dynamic multibody simulation is carried out. If the wheel profile is unfeasible, the Optimiser will try to fix it (see 2.4.4). Afterwards the results are sent to the Optimiser, assessed and stored for further choice of the optimum solution.

Fig. 9 Optimisation algorithm outline

2.5. Multibody simulation models

2.5.1. Vehicle model

For the purposes of the optimisation process we used a multibody model of a five section, fully low-floor, articulated tram supported on three non-pivoting bogies with independent wheelsets (the first section schematic is shown in Fig. 10). The outmost cars are set on motor bogies and the central one on trailer bogie. Apart from its function and tractive

equipment, all bogies are similar. The initial wheel profile was set to PST, the typical tram wheel profile in Poland. For wheel-rail contact we used the FASTSIM algorithm due to high demand in computation speed. The solver sampling was set to 200 Hz. The following coordinate system was adopted: longitudinal axis X in direction of ride, lateral axis Y positive to the right looking towards X , vertical axis Z positive downwards.

Fig. 10 Vehicle model topology (first section)

Tab. 2 Main parameters of the vehicle model

parameter	notation	value
wheel rubber insert stiffness coefficient along all axes	k_r	50 MN/m
wheel rubber insert damping coefficient along all axes	d_r	30 kNs/m
primary suspension stiffness coefficient along the X axis	k_{1x}	5.0 MN/m
primary suspension stiffness coefficient along the Y axis	k_{1y}	5.0 MN/m
primary suspension stiffness coefficient along the Z axis	k_{1z}	0.7 MN/m
secondary suspension stiffness coefficient along the X axis	k_{2x}	0.15 MN/m
secondary suspension stiffness coefficient along the Y axis	k_{2y}	0.15 MN/m
secondary suspension stiffness coefficient along the Z axis	k_{2z}	see (4)
primary suspension damping coefficient along the X axis	d_{1x}	10 kNs/m
primary suspension damping coefficient along the Y axis	d_{1y}	10 kNs/m
primary suspension damping coefficient along the Z axis	d_{1z}	0.4 kNs/m
secondary suspension damping coefficient along the X axis	d_{2x}	2.4 kNs/m
secondary suspension damping coefficient along the Y axis	d_{2y}	2.4 kNs/m
secondary suspension damping coefficient along the Z axis	d_b	9.9 kNs/m
car joint stiffness coefficient along all axes	k_j	80 MN/m
car joint damping coefficient along all axes	d_j	32 kNs/m
bogie base	b	1850 mm
distance between bogies	w	11500 mm
rolling circles gauge	r	1500 mm
wheel radius	R	330 mm
wheel-rail friction coefficient	μ	0.36

Tab. 3 Mass parameters of the vehicle model

	mass [kg]	I_{xx} [kgm ²]	I_{yy} [kgm ²]	I_{zz} [kgm ²]
car 1	6500	12398	24330	28691
car 2	5000	11298	16651	20981
car 3	4100	6838	8074	8852
car 4	5200	11824	17381	21920
car 5	5700	10991	21570	25446
bogie frame	1000	408	557	882
motor (4 per bogie)	550	11	38	37
wheelset	500	150	26.2	150
wheel rim	130	6	11	6

The main parameters of the vehicle model were listed in Tab. 2 and Tab 3. Cars are connected with 4 elastic joints: 3 upper and 1 lower. The primary suspension was modelled with 8 force elements (2 per wheel). Non-linear airspring elements are used as the secondary suspension, taking into account non-linear damping of the air moving in the pipes between the airbag and an additional volume tank. There is also an auxiliary spring with non-linear stiffness (Fig. 11) and zero damping connected in series with the airspring. The total force $F(z)$ in the secondary suspension element is an aggregate of the pneumatic airbag force $F_p(z)$, and parallel airbag damping force F_d , calculated according to the formula (4). The thermodynamic changes in the airspring are assumed to be polytropic.

$$F(z) = \overbrace{A_{ef} \cdot p_0 \cdot \left(V_{t0} \cdot \left(V_{t0} + \left(A_{ef} + \frac{dV}{dz} \right) z - Ax \right)^{-1} \right)^n}^{F_p(z)} + \overbrace{d_{2z} \dot{z}_t}^{F_d} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 11 Auxiliary spring characteristics

A_{ef} stands for the effective area in the working state, which is an assumed constant, z – vertical airbag deflection, p_0 – atmospheric pressure (constant), V_{t0} – initial total volume, $\frac{dV}{dz}$ – volume change due to deflection, A – cross-section area of the pipe connecting the airspring with the additional tank, x – theoretical displacement of the air mass in the pipe to the additional volume tank, \dot{z}_t – relative velocity of the airbag including the auxiliary spring, d_{2z} – damping coefficient of the airbag material along the Z axis. Initial total volume consists of the airbag volume V_b and the additional volume V_{ad} . Additional parameters concerning the airspring are listed in Tab. 4.

Tab. 4 Parameters of the airspring model

parameter	notation	value
effective area of airspring	A_{ef}	0.118 m ²
initial total volume	V_{t0}	0.0071 m ³
volume change due to deflection along the Z axis	dV/dz	-0.053 m ³ /m
additional volume (tank)	V_{ad}	0.015 m ³
atmospheric pressure	p_0	101300 Pa
polytropic exponent	n	1.4
friction coefficient of the air in the pipe	λ	0.017
pipe length	L	0.2 m
pipe inner diameter	d	0.05 m
damping of the airbag material	d_b	0.1 kNs/m
total horizontal damping	d_t	2.5 kNs/m

The dynamic interaction between the airbag and the additional tank is modelled using the following formulas (5).

$$m\ddot{x} + \frac{\rho}{2} \lambda \frac{L}{d} A \dot{x}^2 + (p_b - p)A = 0, m = \rho AL \quad (5)$$

Notation m stands for constant mass of the air in the connecting pipe, ρ – air density in the tank (pressure dependent), λ – friction coefficient of the air in the pipe, L – pipe length, d – pipe inner diameter, p_b – air pressure in the airbag, p – air pressure in the additional tank. Each airspring was accompanied with 2 dampers one lateral and one vertical.

2.5.2. Track model

For the track model we adopted the following sections:

- tangent fast tram track, ≈ 300 m long, $v_{max} = 70$ kmph, good technical condition,
- tangent track, ≈ 100 m long, $v_{max} = 30$ kmph, bad technical condition,
- curved track (curve radii: 22, 25, 50 m), ≈ 200 m long, $v_{max} = 20$ kmph, good technical condition, without superelevation due to track built into the road.

Adopted rail irregularities (Fig. 12) were measured in the tram system of Poznań (Poland).

Fig. 12 Used rail irregularities

The track was assumed as inertia-fixed and applied with measured geometry from respective sections in the city. We used 60R2 rails and 1435 mm gauge, without rail cant.

3. Optimisation results

During the optimisation process we evaluated more than 50 000 feasible wheel profiles. The algorithm found a set of 492 non-dominated profiles. This set is shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13 Non-dominated optimisation results (dots) in comparison with baseline wheel profiles (crosses)

The axes in the above plots correspond to the three optimisation criteria: wear index I_w , Y/Q_{ratio} and contact area A_c . Each result in the plot corresponds to a single wheel profile. The crosses correspond to the baseline “known” profiles while the dots to the non-dominated solutions to the problem found by the CMA-ES algorithm. The number of the non-dominated solutions is high and in some areas of the space, the solutions are placed densely. In order to limit the number of solutions in the Pareto set, we removed some of them based on the fitness similarity criterion. If two solutions were too similar to each other (arbitrarily selected to leave less than 20 results), then one of them was removed. The similarity function was defined by the following thresholds (6):

$$\begin{aligned}
 eps_contact_area &= 4 * 10^{-6} \\
 eps_yq &= 0.04 \\
 eps_wear_index &= 40
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{6}$$

The resulting set of 16 solutions dispersed over the search space is shown in Fig. 14. It can be seen that resultant wheel profiles dominated all baseline ones, regarding all three optimisation criteria. The optimisation criteria values of the set of 16 best solutions are gathered in Tab. 5.

Fig. 14 Selected optimisation results (dots) in comparison with baseline wheel profiles (crosses)

Tab. 5 List of optimisation criteria values for the selected profiles

id	name	I_w [N]	Y/Q_{ratio} [-]	A_c [m ²]	equivalent conicity [-]	flange width [mm]
1	001493	792.78	0.35	8.48E-05	0.01	15.19
2	004918	581.45	0.45	6.33E-05	0.08	14.97
3	001955	677.44	0.47	8.37E-05	0.04	14.93
4	005093	619.45	0.52	9.09E-05	0.05	15.21
5	000066	557.49	0.54	8.40E-05	0.05	15.60
6	000022	500.87	0.55	2.88E-05	0.60	15.90
7	003536	440.48	0.60	7.94E-05	0.04	15.66
8	000013	508.00	0.63	8.34E-05	0.04	15.82
9	000003	391.36	0.67	1.72E-07	0.09	16.16
10	009388	326.38	0.72	8.31E-05	0.07	15.33
11	010426	318.96	0.78	8.84E-05	0.05	15.37
12	004911	276.85	0.93	1.45E-06	0.45	18.47
13	002861	278.91	1.00	1.01E-05	0.47	18.55
14	000805 (PP7)	277.92	1.06	3.77E-05	0.35	18.30
15	000287	276.78	1.20	4.64E-05	0.26	18.47
16	001663	276.90	1.27	5.53E-05	0.47	18.49

The resultant profiles present a wide variety of optimisation criteria values. Profile 000805 (hereinafter: PP7) was selected for further investigation, as one which accomplished the following secondary criteria:

- All criteria values should be better than the respective ones for the PST profile (the newest in Poland).
- Wear index should be as low as possible.
- Flange width should be as big as possible to ensure sufficient wear margin.

PP7 shows the best compliance with those conditions. It should be noted that even the Y/Q_{ratio} exceeds 1, the result is still better by around 18 % in comparison with the PST profile that is in use (1.29 for PST). Interaction of rounded flange outer side (close to the flange tip) with the rail at high angle of attack may result in climbing. The flange side here was considered too steep regarding interaction with crossings (switching rail), hence we decided to change it to a 70 ° inclined straight line (after the original PST profile), which did not influence the simulation results. Fig. 15 presents the altered PP7 profile (solid line) in

comparison to the PST profile (dashed line), and the range of flange tip modification (dash-dotted line).

Fig. 15 Outlines of wheel profiles: PST (baseline) and PP7 (optimised)

The optimised wheel profile was altered mainly in the flange and flange root section. Due to the demanding nature of tram wheel-rail interface operation (frequent flanging in curves or worn out tangent sections) this algorithm's course of action is intelligible. Those inconsistent conditions of wheel-rail interaction make optimisation of the tram wheel profile highly challenging. The flange root is less concave than for the PST profile, but the flange itself is thinner, below $z = -10$. The proposed wheel profile also consists mainly of splines, which means that it is impossible to measure the subsequent curves given their radii. Also, the outer flange side is a spline for the most part. This makes calculating the Nadal criterion problematic, due to inconstant flange inclination value. It might be measured as an angle between a horizontal line and a tangent to flange at a specific vertical coordinate. In Polish tram regulations there are no solutions for such a problem.

Fig. 16 Relationships of wear index (a) and Y/Q ratio (b) to wheel flange width

The optimisation algorithm reached a wear index limit while computing the new wheel profile (see Fig. 16a). It seems to be dependent on the flange width value and can be described with line $y = -8.18x + 428.79$, where y means wear index and x means flange width. The optimisation algorithm was unable to find any better results exceeding the line toward lower values of wear index. In this case, a wider flange (18-21.3 mm) enabled achieving the lowest wear index. On the other hand, a narrower flange resulted in slightly higher minimum values of wear index, but there were also significantly worse results in that range (14-18 mm). Wheel profiles which achieved the lowest values of wear index simultaneously achieved the top values of Y/Q_{ratio} , due to low flangeway clearance. Flange widths around 21.5 mm result in zero wheel-rail play and those solutions were automatically rejected by the optimisation algorithm. In other words, even if we manage to exceed the wear index limit, the resultant

wheel profiles will be likely rejected due to high derailment risk. Fig. 16b clearly confirms the highly important role of lateral play in the formation of the Y/Q coefficient. Due to wheel profile geometry the play is approximately inversely proportional to flange width, with the assumption that flange width increases towards the external side of the track. The linear relationship could be expressed with the formula $y = 0.15x - 1.70$, with the coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.82$, where y means Y/Q_{ratio} and x means flange width. The relationship of the contact area and flange width was without any clear trend. The resultant wheel profiles with flange width included in the range 14.0-17.5 mm had a greater contact area than the others.

Ride comfort values were checked according to EN 12299 [26] in order to determine the influence of the optimisation process (Fig. 17). The results are derived from the first car of the vehicle, for a passenger standing in the middle. The N_{MV} value for the PST profile was given as a reference. According to EN 12299 all the results are comprised in the range of comfortable conditions ($1.5 \leq N_{MV} < 2.5 \text{ m/s}^2$), hence changes introduced to the geometry of the wheel profile did not significantly affect ride comfort. The PP7 profile (000805) gave almost the same value of N_{MV} and since increasing the ride comfort was not included in the aims of the optimisation process it can be counted among the positives that the value is not deteriorated.

Fig. 17 Ride comfort N_{MV} values

4. The new wheel profile assessment

The new wheel profile produced a smoother rolling radius difference (RRD) with the 60R2 rail (Fig. 18). The biggest difference occurred for the displacements range corresponding to flange contact, that is where the most intensive wear takes place due to high creep forces [27]. We also managed to remove the sudden bend in the equivalent conicity plot between an amplitude between 3 and 5 mm, which may contribute to instability when running on faster track sections [28]. The PP7 plot is free from that phenomenon and in general has a calmer course.

Fig. 18 RRD, equivalent conicity and contact patch distribution plots of PST and PP7 profiles

Fig. 18 presents all possible contact spots on the discussed wheel profiles and 60R2 rails for $\pm 10 \text{ mm}$ lateral displacement. For low running speed and an uneven technical state of tracks, equal distribution of contact points works better regarding wheel uniform wear, which was confirmed by the simulation results [29].

The main goal of the optimisation process and the most desired feature of the PP7 profile is reduced wear rate. Simulation results show (Fig. 19) that in low radius curves (around 20 m) the average wear index I_w was reduced by around 28 % for the outer wheel and by around 9 % for the inner wheel.

Fig. 19 Y/Q_{ratio} and wear index (I_w) values (curve $R = 22 \text{ m}$)

The Y/Q was also improved, the maximum values were lowered by around 5 % for the outer wheel, and around 3 % for the inner wheel. A considerably greater improvement was achieved on tangent track in poor technical condition (Fig. 20).

Fig. 20 Y/Q_{ratio} on tangent track with measured irregularities (WS1R)

Application of the PP7 profile allowed for a reduction in peak value of Y/Q_{ratio} by around 55 %. Those peaks may deteriorate ride safety, although, as it was executed in this study, it is possible to reduce them by altering the shape of the wheel profile. Simulation results proved that wheel lateral play strongly influences the derailment coefficient Y/Q_{ratio} (Fig. 21).

Fig. 21 Influence of variable play on Y/Q_{ratio} (PST profile, play values indicated above the plot)

The plot presents calculations from the same tangent section of track with real track irregularities, but for different values of wheelset gauge causing the change of lateral wheel play (from 2 to 8 mm and 4 to 16 mm for whole wheelset). The nominal play is around 4 mm (see Fig. 25). Increasing the play by just 1 mm (to 5 mm) caused a decrease of around 50 % in Y/Q_{ratio} . Further alterations of play did not have a more beneficial result, rather a deterioration of wear index (Fig. 16, play controlled with flange width). From this comes the conclusion that the flangeway clearance should be increased by at least 1 mm for the PST profile to improve ride safety.

In contrast to the PST profile, PP7 produced mostly single point (patch) contact while curving (Fig. 22), which means lower creepage and wear. The contact of the new profile acted more steadily during entering the curve (50-52 s) on the outer wheel and during exiting (66-70 s) on both wheels. Due to the almost equal distribution of contact area between two patches formed by the PST profile and rail on the outer wheel, the contact area of the PST profile stands for the sum of two contact patches. Other contact patches for both wheel profiles were omitted due to their negligibly low contact area. The contact area was slightly larger for PP7 profile during the longer part of the run. This feature is visible mostly while riding on curves. On tangent track the tendency is the opposite.

Fig. 22 Number of contact patches and contact area values (curve $R = 22\text{ m}$)

Fig. 23 Contact patch evolution during entering $R = 25\text{ m}$ curve (PST – plain, PP7 – striped), description in text

The location and shape of contact patches while entering the curve ($R = 25\text{ m}$) for both analysed wheel profiles can be seen in Fig. 23. Right before the curve the patches were similar and a slight lateral displacement occurred between them (Fig. 23a). After entering the curve, the PST contact patch began to widen and then split into two areas located on the flange root and flange side (Fig. 23b). The vertical axis of symmetry of the whole contact was interrupted by the increasing angle of attack, while the PP7 profile formed an elliptic, single contact patch which did not split, but widened considerably on the wheel flange (Fig. 23c and Fig. 23d). Greater dispersion of the contact area from its centre provoked the occurrence of greater creepage and, after likely contact saturation, slip. Along with the movement of the wheel laterally towards the outside of the track the contact area for the optimised wheel profile was nearly constant, up to -2 mm of displacement, then it dropped to reach -5 mm of displacement (Fig. 24). Two contact patches for the PST profile were taken into consideration due to the similar values of contact area at the end of the lateral play range. The contact area of the PST profile (first contact patch) increased from the initial position of the wheel to around -1 mm of lateral displacement, then rapidly fell until reaching the flange contact. The second contact patch of PST profile was activated only after reaching the wheel flange (two point contact). The contact surface magnitude increased after reaching the wheel flange for both wheel profiles. A slightly increased contact area for $\pm 1.5 - 4.0\text{ mm}$ lateral displacements of the wheel seems to be profitable regarding RCF formation during hunting

movement, but it can also intensify wear due to a larger share of slip in contact [30]. The contact angle is strongly associated with rolling radius and wheel curvature [31]. No contact jumps were noticed from the initial “0” position of the wheel on rail to just before the flange contact for both examined profiles (Fig. 25). Those were spotted only during flange contact.

Fig. 24 Contact area vs. wheel lateral displacement (curve $R = 25\text{ m}$, outer wheel)

Fig. 25 Contact angle vs. wheel lateral displacement (curve $R = 25\text{ m}$, outer wheel)

5. Conclusions

A bio-inspired genetic algorithm of tram wheel profile optimisation was described. Over 50000 feasible wheel profiles were generated, including the new wheel profile, PP7, selected for the city of Poznań. Interesting tendencies were observed on the set of non-dominated optimisation results. There was a non-linear trade-off between wear index and Y/Q_{ratio} and a suchlike relationship was found for the Y/Q_{ratio} and flange width, but here the dependence was close to linear. Also, a lower limit of wear index was recognised, which was not to be exceeded for the optimisation algorithm with subsequent generations of candidate solutions in given ride conditions. Moreover, this limit appeared to be counter-proportional to the value of flange width. The PP7 profile appeared to have a smoother course of RRD function and monotonically increasing conicity plot in opposition to the PST profile. The above was also visible in even distribution of contact patches, which contributed to a lower number of contact patches occurring simultaneously. Two contact patches while riding in a low radius curve for the PST profile were exchanged into one for PP7. The new profile also managed to prevent the contact patch from performing sudden jumps between distant locations on the wheel profile, which might accelerate wear. The wear index was reduced by as much as 28 % and the Y/Q_{ratio} decreased by up to 55 % in comparison to the PST profile. We confirmed that flangeway clearance has a great influence on the derailment coefficient and wear index. The actual PST profile has too small a flangeway clearance and this is, to a considerable extent, the cause of worse results than for PP7. It was found that the PP7 profile gave a greater contact area on both wheels while running on a curve, which may decrease the predisposition to rolling contact fatigue.

It is obvious that wheel profiles change their shape during operation. This is particularly severe while introducing a new wheel profile to a network whose rail profiles are “fitted” to the current wheel profile. After some time, the new wheel profile should change into the worn wheel profile typical for the considered rail system. To take full advantage of the new PP7

profile, it should begin to be used on a network fitted with unworn rails and preferably having the whole fleet based on one type of vehicle. Alternatively, the operator may change the wheel profile for the whole operating rolling stock and wait some time for the rails to adjust to the new wheel profile, which should last for some generations of worn wheels. For this reason, it is likely to experience increased wheel and rail wear intensity due to the lapping process if the wheel and rail profiles are mismatched. Another difficulty is that tram operators usually use several types of vehicles in one system, which may wear wheels and rails in different ways. Maybe a family of optimised wheel profiles would be the most beneficial in this application. Nevertheless, this issue has to be investigated more deeply.

The proposed wheel profile justifies the expectations of better performance and durability of tram wheels in Poznań, which have to be preceded with supervised operation and verification of the simulation results. Wheel profiles comprise flange tip, with its shape that may also be optimised for tram systems where shallow-grooved crossings are present. This is an important issue, which also should be dealt with.

At the time of preparing this manuscript, the optimisation methodology is undergoing validation by supervised operation on one tram carrying out regular transport work.

Acknowledgements

All the presented work has been realised within the framework of the “Identification and modelling of nonlinear phenomena at the wheel/rail contact area for the development of a new tramway wheel profile” research project (LIDER/20/521/L-4/12/NCBR/2013), that began with financial support from the National Centre for Research and Development. The work was co-financed by the Faculty of Transport Engineering, Poznan University of Technology, 05/52/DSMK/0286.

Declaration of interest

Declarations of interest: none.

References

- [1] B. Liu, T.X. Mei, S. Bruni, Design and optimisation of wheel-rail profiles for adhesion improvement, *Veh. Syst. Dyn.* 54 (2016) 429–444. doi:10.1080/00423114.2015.1137958.
- [2] I.Y. Shevtsov, V.L. Markine, C. Esveld, Design of railway wheel profile taking into account rolling contact fatigue and wear, *Wear.* 265 (2008) 1273–1282. doi:10.1016/j.wear.2008.03.018.
- [3] H. Wu, Effects of wheel and rail profiles on vehicle performance, *Veh. Syst. Dyn.* 44 (2006) 541–550. doi:10.1080/00423110600875393.
- [4] I. Persson, R. Nilsson, U. Bik, M. Lundgren, S. Iwnicki, Use of a genetic algorithm to improve the rail profile on Stockholm underground, *Veh. Syst. Dyn.* 48 (2010) 89–104. doi:10.1080/00423111003668245.
- [5] O. Polach, D. Nicklisch, Wheel/rail contact geometry parameters in regard to vehicle behaviour and their alteration with wear, *Wear.* 366–367 (2016) 200–208. doi:10.1016/j.wear.2016.03.029.
- [6] T. Staśkiewicz, B. Firlik, W. Jaśkowski, L. Wittenbeck, On designing a durable and safe tram wheel profile, in: M. Spiriyagin, T. Gordon, C. Cole, T. McSweeney (Eds.), *Proc. 25th Int. Symp. Dyn. Veh. Roads Tracks (IAVSD 2017)*, CRC Press, Leiden, 2018.
- [7] J. Santamaria, J. Herreros, E.G. Vadillo, N. Correa, Design of an optimised wheel profile for rail vehicles operating on two-track gauges, *Veh. Syst. Dyn.* 51 (2013) 54–73. doi:10.1080/00423114.2012.711478.
- [8] I. Persson, S.D. Iwnicki, Optimisation of Railway Wheel Profiles using a Genetic Algorithm, *Veh. Syst. Dyn.* 41 (2004) 517–526.
- [9] M. Novales, a Orro, M.R. Bugarín, Use of a genetic algorithm to optimize wheel profile

- geometry, *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part F J. Rail Rapid Transit.* 221 (2007) 467–476. doi:10.1243/09544097JRRT150.
- [10] G. Shen, X. Zhong, A design method for wheel profiles according to the rolling radius difference function, *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part F J. Rail Rapid Transit.* 225 (2011) 457–462. doi:10.1177/2041301710394920.
- [11] H. Jahed, B. Farshi, M.A. Eshraghi, A. Nasr, A numerical optimization technique for design of wheel profiles, *Wear.* 264 (2008) 1–10. doi:10.1016/j.wear.2006.06.006.
- [12] J. Gerlici, T. Lack, Railway wheel and rail head profiles development based on the geometric characteristics shapes, *Wear.* 271 (2011) 246–258. doi:10.1016/j.wear.2010.10.052.
- [13] I.Y. Shevtsov, V.L. Markine, C. Esveld, Optimal design of wheel profile for railway vehicles, *Wear.* 258 (2005) 1022–1030. doi:10.1016/j.wear.2004.03.051.
- [14] G. Shen, J.B. Ayasse, H. Chollet, I. Pratt, A unique design method for wheel profiles by considering the contact angle function, *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part F J. Rail Rapid Transit.* 217 (2003) 25–30. doi:10.1243/095440903762727320.
- [15] O. Polach, Wheel profile design for target conicity and wide tread wear spreading, *Wear.* 271 (2011) 195–202. doi:10.1016/j.wear.2010.10.055.
- [16] D. Cui, L. Li, X. Jin, X. Li, Optimal design of wheel profiles based on weighed wheel/rail gap, *Wear.* 271 (2011) 218–226. doi:10.1016/j.wear.2010.10.005.
- [17] M. Ignesti, A. Innocenti, L. Marini, E. Meli, A. Rindi, P. Toni, Wheel profile optimization on railway vehicles from the wear viewpoint, *Int. J. Non. Linear. Mech.* 53 (2013) 41–54. doi:10.1016/j.ijnonlinmec.2012.12.002.
- [18] J. McCall, Genetic algorithms for modelling and optimisation, *J. Comput. Appl. Math.* 184 (2005) 205–222. doi:10.1016/j.cam.2004.07.034.
- [19] M. Paczkowska, Ł. Wojciechowski, G. Kinal, K. Ostrowska, P. Okoniewicz, Analiza efektów zużywania się wybranych obręczy kół tramwajowych w aglomeracji poznańskiej, *Mater. Eng.* 6 (208) (2015) 391–395. doi:10.15199/28.2015.6.8.
- [20] M. Paczkowska, Ł. Wojciechowski, A. Piasecki, Surface morphology of wheels in rail vehicles in urban transport, *J. Achiev. Mater. Manuf. Eng.* 1 (2017) 12–20. doi:10.5604/01.3001.0010.5135.
- [21] G. Kinal, M. Paczkowska, Wpływ eksploatacji na wybrane właściwości warstwy wierzchniej szyn oraz obręczy kół tramwajowych, *Tribologia.* 5 (2015) 41–51.
- [22] C. Bernsteiner, G. Müller, A. Meierhofer, K. Six, D. Künstner, P. Dietmaier, Development of white etching layers on rails: simulations and experiments, *Wear.* 366–367 (2016) 116–122. doi:10.1016/j.wear.2016.03.028.
- [23] N. Hansen, A. Ostermeier, Completely Derandomized Self-Adaptation in Evolution Strategies, *Evol. Comput.* 9 (2001) 159–195. doi:10.1162/106365601750190398.
- [24] T. Voß, N. Hansen, C. Igel, Improved step size adaptation for the MO-CMA-ES, in: *Proc. 12th Annu. Conf. Genet. Evol. Comput. - GECCO '10*, ACM Press, New York, New York, USA, 2010: pp. 487–494. doi:10.1145/1830483.1830573.
- [25] F. De Rainville, F. Fortin, M. Gardner, M. Parizeau, C. Gagné, DEAP: A Python Framework for Evolutionary Algorithms, in: *Companion Proc. Genet. Evol. Comput. Conf. (GECCO 2012)*, 2012: pp. 85–92. doi:10.1145/2330784.2330799.
- [26] EN 12299:2009 Railway applications - Ride comfort for passengers - Measurement and evaluation, (n.d.).
- [27] R. Lewis, R.S. Dwyer-Joyce, U. Olofsson, J. Pombo, J. Ambrósio, M. Pereira, C. Ariardo, N. Kuka, Mapping railway wheel material wear mechanisms and transitions, *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part F J. Rail Rapid Transit.* 224 (2010) 125–137. doi:10.1243/09544097JRRT328.
- [28] S. Finke, T. Piechowiak, K. Bryk, A. Sienicki, Proposal to modify the wheel profile of Poznan Fast Tram, *Rail Veh.* (2016) 46–54.
- [29] V.L. Markine, I.Y. Shevtsov, C. Esveld, An inverse shape design method for railway wheel profiles, *Struct. Multidiscip. Optim.* 33 (2007) 243–253. doi:10.1007/s00158-006-0049-3.
- [30] J. Blanco-Lorenzo, J. Santamaria, E.G. Vadillo, N. Correa, On the influence of

conformity on wheel–rail rolling contact mechanics, *Tribol. Int.* 103 (2016) 647–667.
doi:10.1016/j.triboint.2016.07.017.

[31] S. Iwnicki, *Handbook of Railway Vehicle Dynamics*, CRC Press, 2006.